

The effect of high temperatures on Portland cement stone

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Annotation: *Under high temperature conditions, the compounds bind $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, thereby helping the cement to be as strong and of a specific structure as needed when heated and cooled.*

Key words: *apparent chamotte, chromite, magnesite, physicochemical changes*

At temperatures below zero (in a dry environment), no physicochemical changes occur in the cement stone. However, as long as it is exposed to a much higher temperature for a certain period of time, the consistency will begin to change. For example, at a temperature of 200 °C, the strength of Portland cement-based concrete decreases by about 50%, and this strength is not restored even after the heat source is removed. As the temperature increases, the strength of concrete decreases. For example, if concrete is heated to a temperature of 500... 550 °C and moistened, the cement structure will be damaged; at this temperature $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ decomposes into calcium oxide (CaO) and water, when the cement stone is wetted the lime inside the stone is extinguished again and the stone is broken.

At present, methods have been developed to create cement that can withstand very high temperatures, such as 1000... 1300 °C, and can be used in the coating of various heating devices. The addition of fine chamotte, chromite, magnesite and other minerals increases the resistance of Portland cement to high temperatures. Under high temperature conditions, the compounds bind $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, thus helping the cement to remain as strong and have a specific structure as needed when heated and cooled.

This means that Portland cement has very valuable building properties, i.e. it is extremely durable, its strength increases relatively quickly, and it is also resistant to various adverse environmental influences. It is also relatively cheap to get. This allows for a high degree of mechanization of portland cement production.

At a time when precast concrete and reinforced concrete structures are increasingly used in industrial construction, it is extremely important to produce a large number of valuable binding materials such as portland cement and use them sparingly.

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